

Search for New Design Elements in Time-Honoured Shops in Tainan – On Curriculum Practice about Culture Creative Industry

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Abstract : This paper mainly discusses the research and practice process of a laboratory curriculum by leading students to perform field investigation into time-honoured shops that have existed for more than 50 years in the downtown area of Tainan, Taiwan, and then search again for design elements and completing the design. The participants are juniors from the Department of Visual Communication Design, Kun Shan University. The duration of research and practice is two months. Operators of these shops are invited to jointly appraise the final achievements. 9 works out of 27 are chosen for final exhibition and commercialization.

Keywords : culture creative industry, visual communication design, curriculum experimental, visual arts

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